

In the present study, convenience sampling was used to recruit Iranian university students. Participants were recruited between October 1 and October 29, 2024, via social media platforms (e.g., WhatsApp and Telegram academic groups). The survey was administered online through Porsline¹.

Inclusion criteria required participants to be currently enrolled Iranian university students, able to read Persian, and willing to complete the electronic questionnaire. Exclusion criteria included not being a university student or being unable to read Persian.

Before accessing the questionnaire, participants provided electronic informed consent after reading a description of the study purpose, confidentiality assurances, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. No identifying information (e.g., names, student numbers, IP addresses) was collected. Measures were taken to prevent duplicate responses (e.g., single submission settings). The final sample consisted of 319 students.

Because the online survey was programmed with forced-response settings, participants were required to complete each item before submission. Consequently, the dataset contains no item-level missing data. Participants retained the option to discontinue participation at any time by exiting the survey prior to submission.

Important note: Reverse-keyed items were recoded before public release of the dataset to ensure consistency in scoring direction (higher values consistently reflect higher levels of the construct where applicable).

	Variable name	Description	Scale	Coding direction	Question number
1	age	Mean= 24.27 Sdt= 5.120	-	-	-
2	gender	Females = 255 (79.9%) Male = 64 (20.06%)	-	1 = male 2 = female	-
3	degree	bachelor students = 146 (45.8%) master students = 146 (45.8%) doctoral students = 27 (8.5%)	-	1 = bachelor students 2 = master students 3 = doctoral students	-
4	Attachment style	It consists of 3 subscales: 1. secure (Q1, Q6, Q8, Q12, Q13, Q17) 2. avoidant (Q5, Q2, Q16, Q14, Q7, Q18) 3. anxious (Q3, Q4, Q9, Q10, Q11, Q15)	Revised Adult Attachment Scale (RAAS)	-	Q1-Q18
5	procrastination	Higher scores on the scale mean that the person has more procrastination.	Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS)	-	Q19-Q34
6	Self-compassion	Higher scores on the scale mean that the person has more self-compassion.	Short Form of the Self-Compassion Scale (SCS-SF)	-	Q35-Q46
7	Post-traumatic stress disorder	PTSD = Q49-Q54 PTSD dysfunction = Q55-Q57 DSO = Q58-Q63 DSO dysfunction = Q64-Q66 Higher scores on the scale mean that the person has more criteria of PTSD / DSO.	International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ)	-	Q49-Q66
8				1 = less than 6 months ago	

¹ porsline.ir

	<p>Accident time</p>	<p>In the data file, accident time refers to the time spent after trauma experiences and it's part of ITQ.</p>	<p>International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ)</p>	<p>2 = between 6-12 months ago 3 = between 1-5 years ago 4 = between 10-20 years ago 5 = more than 20 years ago</p>	<p>Accident time</p>
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